

TABLE VII

Acid	Oxalic	Citric	Malic	Malonic	Succinic
Mean of relative equilibrium constants 13×10^2			153	86	16.5	2.67	1.17

From the above table an idea about the comparative affinities, relative to tartaric acid, of different acids for complex formation with molybdic acid is obtained. While oxalic acid has more affinity than tartaric acid, citric acid has got slightly less and malic acid has still less affinity. The affinities of the other two acids, viz., malonic and succinic acids are much smaller.

Referring to Table VI, phenols, phenolic acid and alcohols appear to have negligible affinities for complex formation in presence of tartaric acid.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES OF COMPLEX FORMATION BETWEEN
MOLYBDIC AND TARTARIC ACIDS. PART III. ULTRAMICROSCOPIC
STUDIES ON THE CHANGE OF PARTICLE NUMBER AND
CATAPHORETIC VELOCITY OF MOLYBDIC ACID SOL
PARTICLES DURING COMPLEX FORMATION

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That an appreciable portion of molybdic acid in its sol is present as true solution and also the presence of tartaric acid in the sol transforms the colloidal particles into solution, have been shown by counting the number of particles per c.c. with an ultramicroscope. The cataphoretic velocity of molybdic acid sol particles, either alone or in presence of tartaric acid at different pH has been studied and the results discussed.

The work of Dumanskii and collaborators (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 60, 1053; *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 48, 49) indicated the existence of a "colloidal complex" when tartaric acid (H_2T) was added to a sodium tungstate solution. This can be advantageously tested if we start with a colloidal solution and follow with a ultramicroscope the change of particle number taking place with the addition of an organic acid.

We started with a molybdic acid sol in which an appreciable percentage of the acid was present as true solution and the sol particles were found to be negatively charged. Dhar and collaborator (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 282) assumed the likely existence of an equilibrium of the type

The negative charge on the particle is chiefly due to the adsorption of α -polymerised anions carrying x units of electric charge and y of simple anions, each carrying one unit of charge. The existence of such an equilibrium is capable of being verified experimentally by ultramicroscopic studies. When a carefully dialysed sol of molybdic acid is observed in a slit ultramicroscope, the number of visible particles per c.c. is generally small (about 10^9 per c.c. in $0.02M$. MoO_3 sol). The molybdic acid mostly exists as invisible micelles or probably even in simple molecular state. If, however, a coagulating electrolyte is added, the number of visible particles increases to about 10^{12} per c.c.

In this type of colloidal acids, bases or ampholytes, the surface charge density σ is determined by surface ionisation and so small changes of H^+ activity of the solution may result in an appreciable variation in the value of σ . Mukherjee and collaborators (*Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1935, I, 47) in a review, have shown that the electrokinetic behaviours of colloidal particles depend mainly on the surface charge density and hence measurement of cataphoretic velocity (C. V.) of molybdic acid sol particles during complex formation with tartaric acid under different conditions, may furnish useful information regarding changes taking place on the surface of the sol particles.

The object of the present investigation is to afford a direct evidence by ultramicroscopic examination, firstly of the existence of an appreciable portion of molybdic acid in its sol in true solution and secondly, of the formation of molybdotartrate complex in the true solution at the expense of colloidal particles. The change of cataphoretic velocity of sol particles in presence of tartaric acid at different concentrations and pH has been measured in order to throw light on the changes taking place on the surface of particles under stated conditions.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Particle Counting.—The number of particles per c.c. in different sols was counted with the help of a slit ultramicroscope. The cell containing the colloidal solution was illuminated with a strong light beam of known thickness using an eye-piece reticule and with a proper stop (slit of known dimensions) only a definite volume of the solution could be made visible through the eye-piece. The sol in question, was diluted properly with optically void water so that particles varying from 2 to 6 in number could come at a time within the field of vision. Such numbers were then counted after definite time intervals, the signal for which was given by the tick from a metronome. The mean of at least 200 such readings was taken in each case and the particle number per c.c. was then calculated. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No. of particles observed in pure MoO_3 sol (0.02 M)	0.83×10^9 per c.c.					
	Do	after addition of electrolyte (HCl) 1.24×10^{12} per c.c.				
Conc. of H_2T (in mols)	0.0	0.49×10^{-2}	0.98×10^{-2}	1.92×10^{-2}	3.92×10^{-2}	5.76×10^{-2}
Ratio $\frac{H_2T}{MoO_3}$	0.0	0.25	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0
No. of particles per c.c.	0.83×10^9	0.18×10^9	0.28×10^9	0.9×10^7	0.36×10^2	Nil

As with the addition of electrolyte for coagulation of MoO_3 in the sol, the particle number per c.c. is enormously increased, the additional particles must have come from MoO_3 present in the true solution. The addition of H_2T in increasing amounts gradually diminishes the number of particles in the resulting mixtures and when the ratio $\text{H}_2\text{T}:\text{MoO}_3=3$, *i. e.*, the mols. of H_2T is 3 times the mols. of molybdic acid in a mixture, no particle is apparently visible in the system. The sol particles are then completely transformed into true solution either as a complex with H_2T or as simple molecules.

It should be noted here that the above figures of particle numbers are not strictly quantitative, but give an approximate idea of the phenomena occurring under the stated conditions.

Cataphoretic Velocity Measurements.—The cataphoretic velocity of particles in different systems is measured in a Mattson's cylindrical cell, the experimental details and arrangements of which are the same as described by Ghosh and collaborator (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 17, 721). The *pH* of the systems under different conditions was adjusted by adding requisite quantity of NaOH and the measurements of C. V. were made one hour after each addition of electrolytes. The results are tabulated below. C. V. is expressed in cm./sec/volt/cm.

TABLE II

Change of cataphoretic velocity of molybdic acid sol particles with pH.

(a) Conc. of MoO_3 in the pure sol = 0.020M								
<i>pH</i>	2.48	2.88	3.60	3.97	4.20	4.64
C.V. $\times 10^4$	-25.6	-25.0	-29.8	-35.6	-37.5	-37.9

TABLE III

Variation of cataphoretic velocity of molybdic acid sol particles in presence of tartaric acid and also with change of pH.

(b) Composition of the sol = 0.0165 M- MoO_3 + 0.0094 M- H_2T		(c) Composition of the sol = 0.0165 M- MoO_3 + 0.0164 M- H_2T		(d) Composition of the sol = 0.0165 M- MoO_3 + 0.0818 M- H_2T	
<i>pH</i>	C.V.	<i>pH</i>	C.V.	<i>pH</i>	C.V.
2.36	-24.4×10^{-6}	2.19	-18.1×10^{-6}	2.01	-15.6×10^{-6}
2.60	-28.2	2.85	-20.2	2.67	-16.9
3.40	-33.4	3.42	-28.2	3.74	-28.7
4.03	-33.1	4.28	-24.2	4.18	-26.1
4.40	-28.0	4.52	-25.7	4.78	-25.0
5.01	-36.8	5.42	-36.4	6.24	-36.0

It appears from Table II that in the case of pure MoO_3 sol particles, the increase of p_H causes the gradual increase of C. V. But in Table III it will be noticed that the presence of increasing amount of H_2T in the sol diminishes the value of C. V. It increases in the beginning, followed by a decrease over a small range near about p_H 4.0. As the p_H is further increased, C. V. increases until the particles disappear from view, the system becoming optically void.

D I S C U S S I O N.

According to Mukherjee (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 1 3) and Mukherjee and collaborators (*loc. cit.*), the double layer round the particles in colloidal solutions is regarded as made up of three parts, viz., the primarily adsorbed layer, the electrically adsorbed layer and the mobile sheet. The surface charge density σ , is given by the net excess of charge of the sign, being the sum of the charges carried by ions present per unit area in the form of primarily and electrically adsorbed ions and this σ is the main factor which determines C. V., and the change of C. V. can be suitably explained according to this hypothesis in preference to that of Guoy and Stern.

The micelles of molybdic acid are negatively charged. The concentration of MoO_3 in the sol is found to influence the value of C. V. It decreases with the increase of concentration of MoO_3 in the sol and this can be readily understood when it is found that the p_H value of the system decreases simultaneously. This causes increased electrical adsorption of hydrogen ions when σ decreases and consequently the value of C. V. diminishes. The presence of increasing amount of H_2T in a MoO_3 sol diminishes the C. V. of particles due probably to the decrease of p_H .

When OH' ions are continuously added to the sol, the density of negative charge on the sol particles continuously increases due to the desorption of electrically adsorbed H ions and thus the C. V. increases.

But in presence of H_2T the behaviour is found to be different. This peculiar change of C. V. can be reconciled if we picture it as adsorption of H_2T by valency forces, the increased ionisation of the adsorbed H_2T with the addition of OH' , when C. V. increases in the beginning, then desorption of adsorbed tartrate ions due to the weakness of the valency bond beyond p_H 4.0; when C.V. is found to decrease the ultimate increase of C. V. may be due to similar reasons as in the case of pure MoO_3 sol. This problem will be dealt with more fully later on.

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